

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Rich**FIRST NAME:** Joy**PROGRAM CODE :** DMCR**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 9%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Why are recommendations important in a dissertation?

- Recommendations have implications for policy, practice, and further research.¹**
- Recommendations are theoretical and not practical.
- Recommendations are highly abstract constructs devised for an academic audience.
- Recommendations primarily focus on the limitations of a study.

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition. (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 317.

2. Where is the bibliography information listed when using the notes-bibliography style in a research paper?

- The bibliography information is located in both the notes and bibliography sections of a research paper.²**
- The bibliography information is located in the notes section at the bottom of the page.
- The bibliography information is located in bibliography section at the end of the research paper.
- The bibliography information is located in notes section at the beginning of the paper.

3. What is the purpose of the introduction section of a dissertation?

- The introduction section orients the reader to the problem that the study is addressing, the purpose of the study, outlines research questions, and explains why the researcher chose to focus on the topic or issue.³**
- The introduction section aims to paint a picture for the reader using current concepts, data, and theories relevant to one's research topic.
- The introduction section outlines the logic and research approach used throughout the research process.

² Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th edition., Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 155.

³ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 74.

- The introduction section interprets the results to verify if they confirm or contradict previous research and existing theory.
4. What is outlined in the methodology section of a dissertation?
- The methodology section is where the researcher outlines the logic and research approach used throughout the research process.⁴**
- The methodology section aims to paint a picture for the reader using current concepts, data, and theories relevant to one's research topic.
- The methodology section interprets the results to verify if they confirm or contradict previous research and existing theory.
- The methodology section orients the reader to the problem that the study is addressing, the purpose of the study, outlines research questions, and explains why the researcher chose to focus on the topic or issue.
5. When using the author-date style in academic writing, where does one list the complete bibliographical information for all the sources they have cited?
- In the reference list at the end of a paper.⁵**
- In the footnotes section at the bottom of the page.
- In the reference list section at the beginning of the paper.
- In the endnotes at the end of the paper.

⁴ Ibid., 183.

⁵ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 223.

6. What is the relevance of the analysis section in a dissertation?
- In the analysis section, the researcher will interpret their results to verify if it confirms or contradicts previous research and existing theory.⁶**
 - The analysis section orients the reader to the problem that the study is addressing, the purpose of the study, outlines research questions, and explains why the researcher chose to focus on the topic or issue.
 - The analysis section aims to paint a picture for the reader using current concepts, data, and theories relevant to one's research topic.
 - The analysis section is where the researcher outlines the logic and research approach used throughout the research process.
7. Why is the literature review section vital to a dissertation?
- The literature review section is where the researcher aims to paint a picture for the reader using current concepts, data, and theories relevant to one's research topic.⁷**
 - The literature review section orients the reader to the problem that the study is addressing, the purpose of the study, outlines research questions, and explains why the researcher chose to focus on the topic or issue.
 - The literature review section is where the researcher outlines the logic and research approach used throughout the research process.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 284.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 141.

- The literature review section is where the researcher will interpret their results to verify if it confirms or contradicts previous research and existing theory.

8. When does one need to use a block quotation?

- A block quotation is used when a quote is more than five lines long.**⁸
- A block quotation differentiates a two-line quote from other text.
- A block quotation is used when a quote is more than three lines long.
- A block quotation is used when the author is unknown.

9. Why is the conclusion section significant in a dissertation?

- The conclusion section is where the researcher makes new connections and ponders broader issues.**⁹
- The conclusion section is where the researcher restates their findings.
- The conclusion section is not vital as the researcher only uses it to end the dissertation.
- The conclusion section is where the researcher discusses whether or not the results confirm or contradict previous research.

⁸ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 361.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 317.

10. How are qualitative findings obtained?

- The researcher must organize and analyze their collected raw data to transform them into research findings.¹⁰**
- The researcher uses only numerical data to analyze the results.
- The researcher does not use data from open-ended questions to analyze the results.
- The researcher uses advanced statistical software to arrive at their findings.

¹⁰ Ibid., 232.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

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